

CHEMICAL EXAMINATION OF THE SEEDS OF *JATROPHA* *GLANDULIFERA*, ROXB.*

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The seeds contain 50% of kernels and 22% of a pale, brownish yellow oil. They are found to contain palmitic, stearic, oleic and linoleic acids; sitosterol (m p 134-35°), a phytosterol (m p. 122-24°), tannin, glucose (osazone, m p 203-204°) and a large amount of a reducing material together with some resinous substance. No acid corresponding to or similar in structure as ricinoleic acid could be isolated from the unsaturated acids.

Jatropha glandulifera is a shrub common at the outskirts of villages in Bengal, Burma, the Northern Circars and Deccan. It is found to grow abundantly on the bunds of tanks. The plant is also prevalent in the waste lands of tropical Africa.

The constituents found in the plant are similar to those of *Jatropha curcas* and also in action. It is purgative, counter-irritant and stimulant. The leaves have a bad taste, act as emmenagogue and are analgesic. They lessen inflammation, asthma, bronchitis, lumbago, and are useful in scorpion-stings. The root is good for piles. The root, brayed with water, is given to children suffering from abdominal enlargements. It purges and is said to reduce glandular swellings. The juice of the plant is used to remove films from the eyes. The fixed oil from the seeds has purgative properties. It is applied to joints in chronic rheumatism, chronic ulcerations, sinuses, ringworm, paralysis and also to foul wounds (Kirtikar and Basu, "Indian Medicinal Plants" 2nd Ed., Vol. III, pp. 2241-2242; Nadkarni, "Indian Materia Medica"; Menon, *J. Soc. Chem. Ind.*, 1910, 29, 1428).

The only mention in the literature regarding the chemical examination of *Jatropha glandulifera* is that of Menon (*loc. cit.*). He has determined some physical constants of the fixed oil from the seeds prepared 4 or 5 years previously and his work is of a very preliminary nature.

The plant belonging to Euphorbiaceae and the oil being a drastic purgative, the latter is usually surmised to be similar to castor oil, particularly with reference to the presence of ricinoleic or other acid of a similar structure. This view is shown to be incorrect in the case of *Jatropha curcas* by Tummin Katti, Alimchandani and Gouder (*J. Univ. Bombay*, 1945, 14, Part III, p. 34). The present investigation was taken up to throw further light on the purgative principle of the seeds with special reference to the nature of the fatty acids in general and of the unsaturated acids in particular.

EXPERIMENTAL

The seeds for the present investigation were collected from places round about Kurnool in Madras Province.

The seeds contain 50% of kernels and 22% of a pale, brownish yellow oil.

* This work formed part of a thesis submitted by R.C. Badam to the University of Bombay for the M.Sc. degree.

Preliminary Examination

The crushed seeds (100 g.) were extracted successively with the following solvents and the extracts dried at 100°.

				Extract.
Petroleum ether (b.p. 30°-60°)	22.2%
Ethyl ether	2.2
Chloroform	0.4
Ethyl acetate	0.6
Ethyl alcohol	2.5
Total				27.9

The seeds were not found to contain any alkaloidal material when tested with Prollius fluid. On distilling 200 g. of the crushed seeds with steam, a very small amount of a pale yellow, oily material was obtained. The aqueous extract of the seeds contained tannins, some reducing material and polysachharides.

The powdered seeds (2.5 kg.) were percolated with cold rectified spirit and the solvent removed from the percolate by distillation under reduced pressure. The syrupy, dark brown residue was dried on fine shreads of filter-paper pulp and extracted successively with petroleum ether, ethyl ether, chloroform, ethyl acetate and ethyl alcohol, and the extracts were examined separately.

Petroleum Ether Extract.—The solvent-free extract was digested with 90% alcohol. (a). The alcohol-soluble portion was saponified and the dry soap extracted with ether. The ether-soluble portion was washed free of soap and digested with charcoal for an hour. The pale yellow extract on repeated crystallisations from 75% alcohol yielded white, shining crystals (m.p. 122-24°) which gave all the characteristic colour tests of phytosterols; the acetate, m.p. 109-10°. The ether-insoluble sodium salts of the fatty acids, mixed with the corresponding salts of the fatty acids from the oil obtained by direct petroleum ether extract of a fresh portion of powdered seeds, were examined separately.

(b). The alcohol-insoluble portion, when worked in like manner as above, gave a phytosterol (m.p. 122-24°; acetate, m. p. 109-10°) and no other compound could be isolated.

Ethyl Ether Extract.—The solvent-free extract was dissolved in chloroform and poured into a flask containing a large excess of petroleum ether (b. p. 60°-80°). No solid separated, but only a brown, viscous, resinous material settled to the bottom of the flask.

This petroleum ether-insoluble resinous material had the consistency of rubber. It had no taste and it did not reduce Fehling's solution. All attempts to get a definite crystalline material from this substance were unsuccessful.

The petroleum ether-soluble portion gave a small amount of a dark oily mass from which nothing definite could be isolated.

Chloroform Extract.—The solvent-free, pale brown extract was dried on a water-bath and dissolved in 80% alcohol and digested with charcoal. On concentrating the filtrate

and keeping overnight, a few white crystalline particles were found to float on the surface; but on further concentration, these particles turned yellow and set to a resinous mass. A portion of this extract reduced Fehling's solution with difficulty but on hydrolysis the reduction was instantaneous, indicating the presence of a polysaccharide. However, all attempts to isolate a definite crystalline compound were unsuccessful.

Ethyl Acetate Extract.—After complete removal of the solvent, the dark brown extract, which was slightly sweet to taste, was digested as above with charcoal, and the filtrate on concentration did not deposit any crystalline material. It readily reduced Fehling's solution, showing the presence of a considerable amount of some reducing material. Nothing crystalline could be isolated from this extract.

Alcohol Extract.—After removal of the last traces of the solvent by distillation under reduced pressure, the sweet, syrupy, dark brown residue was dissolved in water and the solution treated with basic lead acetate. The pale yellow precipitate was filtered and washed with water. It was suspended in water and delead. No solid separated on concentrating the filtrate. It reduced Fehling's solution. A portion of the filtrate on treating with ferric chloride solution was coloured bluish green indicating the presence of tannin. The presence of tannin was further confirmed on treating another portion of the filtrate with potassium dichromate solution yielding a brown precipitate.

Identification of Sugar.—The filtrate and washings, after removing the precipitates of lead salts, were mixed together and delead. The filtrate was concentrated to a syrup. This syrupy residue was distinctly sweet to taste. On digesting the syrup for about 2 hours with redistilled rectified spirit, a very small amount of a white crystalline solid separated which was sweet to taste. This solid could not be worked further for want of sufficient material. However, a small amount of the solution of these crystals readily reduced Fehling's solution.

The syrupy residue, left after removal of the rectified spirit from the filtrate from above, yielded an osazone which on recrystallisation from pyridine and alcohol, melted sharply at 203-204°, indicating the presence of glucose. No other compound could be isolated from the alcoholic extract.

Fatty Oil

The crushed seeds (2 kg.) were extracted with petroleum ether (b.p. 30°-60°) in a modified soxhlet (Tummin Katti, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1930, 7, 210) continuously for about 24 hours and the solvent removed. The purified oil had the following constants :

Ref. index at 27°	1.4672	Iodine value (Hanus)	121.5
Sp. gr. at 27°	0.9216	Reichert-Meissl value	0.5234
Sapon. value	209.1	Hehner value	91.6 %
Acetyl value	16.46	Unsapon. matter	1.53 %

Mixed Fatty Acids

The oil (205 g.) was saponified and the resulting dry hard soap was extracted with ether in a soxhlet to obtain the unsaponifiable matter. The residual soap powder was freed from ether and mixed with the sodium salts of fatty acids obtained from the alcoholic extract of the seeds, as mentioned before, and the fatty acids were liberated and purified. The mixed free fatty acids had the following constants: mixed fatty acids, 91.7 %; mean M.W., 275.5; iodine value (Hanus), 126.2.

The mixed free fatty acids (150 g. approx.) were separated into saturated and unsaturated acids by Twitchell's lead-salt-alcohol method (*Ind. Eng. Chem.*, 1921, 13, 806). The liberated saturated and unsaturated acids had the following constants.

	Saturated.	Unsaturated.
Percentage	13.1	86.9
Mean M.W.	266.9	287.0
Iodine value (Hanus)	5.2	135.0

Liquid Fatty Acids

The liquid acids were esterified with absolute methyl alcohol in the usual manner and 49 g. of these methyl esters were distilled under 10 mm. pressure.

Fraction.	Temp. range.	Wt.	M.W.	Iodine value (Hanus).
I	up to 150°	2.3 g.	240.0	60.4
II	150°-165°	1.5	255.5	68.9
III	165°-185°	2.4	280.0	89.7
IV	185°-195°	5.6	286.2	100.2
V	195°-209°	18.2	287.4	102.4
VI	209°-210°	4.8	288.1	114.3
VII	Residue	14.2	288.6	119.8
		Total 49.0		

Fractions I and II probably consisted of decomposition products; and hence, fractions III—VII were selected for further investigation.

Fractions III—VI were mixed together and about 5 g. of the ester mixture were saponified and oxidised according to the method of Lapworth and Mottram (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1925, 1628). From the mixture of hydroxy-acids, thus obtained, the following were isolated.

CHEMICAL EXAMINATION OF THE SEEDS OF *JATROPHA GLANDULIFERA* 527

Acids.	M.p	M.W. (found).	M.W. (calc.
Dihydroxystearic	134°-135°	315 .	316.4 (oleic)
Tetrahydroxystearic	154°-155°	347	348.4 (linoleic)

A portion of fraction VII was saponified and the liberated acids were brominated according to the method of Eibner and Muggenthaler (Lewkowitsch, "Chemical Technology and Analysis of Oils and Fats", 6th Ed., Vol. I, p. 585). A white crystalline compound, tetrabromostearic acid (m. p. 113-14°) was obtained, indicating the presence of linoleic acid in the liquid acid mixture. From the filtrate no hexabromostearic acid could be isolated.

Thus the liquid unsaturated acids were found to contain only oleic and linoleic acids.

Solid Fatty Acids

The mixture of solid acids were converted into their methyl esters in the usual manner and 19 g. of the ester mixture were distilled under 15 mm. pressure.

Fraction.	Temp. range.	Wt.	M.W.	Fraction.	Temp. range.	Wt.	M.W.	
I	below 194°	3.23 g.	259.3	V	197°-199°	2.90 g.	285.4	
II	below 194°	2.83	256.2	VI	199°-202°	1.80	286.9	
III	194°-195°	2.12	268.2	VII	202° and above	1.39	286.3	
IV	195°-197°	3.45	283.5	VIII	Residue.	1.28	286.7	
Total							19.00	

Fractions I & II.—From each of these fractions pure palmitic acid (m.p. 61.5°; M.W. 255.4) was isolated as the principal constituent. The identity of the palmitic acid was further established by taking a mixed m.p. with an authentic pure sample.

Fraction III.—From this fraction a small amount of palmitic acid (m.p. 61°; M.W. 257) was isolated. The filtrate gave an acid, m.p. 58-59°, with M.W. of 267, probably a mixture of palmitic and stearic acids.

Fraction IV.—From this fraction an acid which melted at 63-69° and with a M.W. of 282 was isolated. The filtrate gave an acid (m.p. 57-58°; M.W. 270), which could not be improved further.

Fractions V - VII.—From each of these fractions pure stearic acid (m.p. 68-69°; M.W. 284.3) was isolated. The melting point remained unchanged on mixing with pure stearic acid.

Thus from the solid acid mixture, only palmitic and stearic acids could be isolated.

Unsaponifiable Matter

This was a reddish, oily, semi-solid material. On digesting repeatedly with charcoal in 95% alcohol and crystallising the product, pure white crystalline compound answering to all the colour tests of phytosterols was obtained. It melted at 134-35° and yielded an acetate melting at 121-22°. This substance is therefore identified as sitosterol. No other compound could be isolated from the mother-liquor.

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